

INTERACTIVE APPROACHES TO TEACHING ENGLISH GRAMMAR: CAROUSEL, SNOWBALL, AND PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING IN DEVELOPING GRAMMATICAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE TEACHERS

Z. Shermatova

Doctoral student of Chirchik state pedagogical university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15645552>

Abstract. *This article explores modern interactive methods for teaching English grammar to future educators, emphasizing their role in developing grammatical competence. The focus is placed on three pedagogical technologies: the Carousel method, the Snowball method, and Problem-Based Learning (PBL). Each approach is analyzed in terms of its application to mastering complex grammatical structures, especially Passive Voice. The study highlights the advantages of these methods, including improved memorization, increased motivation, development of communicative skills, and critical thinking. At the same time, the article examines the potential challenges of implementation—such as differing student levels, time constraints, and the need for teacher preparation—and offers practical recommendations for overcoming them. By integrating these approaches into grammar instruction, educators can create a more dynamic, learner-centered, and effective language learning environment.*

Keywords: *english grammar teaching, passive voice, grammatical competence, interactive learning, carousel method, snowball method, problem-based learning (PBL), communicative approach, teacher training, language pedagogy, grammar games, collaborative learning, critical thinking, learner autonomy.*

Modern education is undergoing an active transformation, which is associated with changes in approaches to teaching and the integration of new technologies into the educational process. In this context, the grammatical competence of future English teachers plays an important role, as not only their professional training but also the quality of students' education depends on it. Expanding the use of interactive technologies is a relevant strategy that helps improve this competence.

Grammar as a component of language competence requires students to have a deep understanding of the structure of the language. Traditional teaching methods, such as lectures and written assignments, are sometimes insufficient to develop lasting grammar skills. Interactive technologies, including various digital resources, games, collaborative learning platforms, and other active methods, offer new ways to engage students in the process of learning grammar. One of the important aspects of implementing interactive technologies is to create a comfortable educational environment where students feel free to learn. Participation in discussions and games allows students to receive instant feedback, which is critical for their confidence in using the language. Using interactive platforms such as Kahoot or Quizlet, you can organize exciting quizzes where grammar rules in a game form begin to be perceived more naturally and easily.

Thus, the carousel method is an interactive way of studying grammar, in which students consistently interact with different interlocutors, performing language exercises in the format of

short dialogues. During the work, one student asks a question or offers a task, and the other must answer correctly, using a given grammatical construction. At certain intervals, students change partners, repeating the exercise several times, which contributes to better assimilation of the material. This method is especially useful for practicing complex grammatical structures, such as verb tenses, conditional sentences or passive voice. Thanks to multiple repetitions and changing interlocutors, students not only remember the rules, but also learn to apply them in speech. The Carousel method makes the process of learning grammar more dynamic, reduces the language barrier and increases students' confidence in using the studied constructions. This method is also suitable for practicing sentence structure. For example, one student can ask a question using a certain grammatical construction, and the other must answer correctly, observing the appropriate form. Gradually, thanks to multiple repetitions in different variations, students get used to the grammar rules and begin to use them automatically. Within the framework of Passive voice, an alternative option would be a task to replace the active voice with the passive voice. For example, when studying the passive voice, the teacher can hand out cards with sentences in the active voice to students. Students in the outer circle read the sentence to their partners, and they must correctly transform it into the passive voice. After the answer, the interlocutor gives an explanation or corrects possible errors. Then, at the signal of the teacher, the outer circle moves, and the process is repeated with a new interlocutor:

Active voice: They built this bridge in 1990.

Passive voice: This bridge was built in 1990.

This approach helps students not only remember the rules of sentence transformation, but also consolidate them through multiple repetition with different interlocutors. The Carousel helps reduce stress before speaking, since communication takes place in pairs, without pressure from the whole group. Students feel more confident, since mistakes are perceived as part of the learning process. This is especially important when studying complex grammar structures that require multiple repetitions. Although the Carousel method is an effective tool for practicing grammar and developing speech skills, it is also not without certain disadvantages. Firstly, difficulties may arise in a group with different levels of preparation: stronger students complete tasks faster, and weaker ones get lost or copy the answers, which reduces individual activity and the effectiveness of assimilation. Secondly, if there is insufficient discipline in the class, the method can turn into formal repetition, losing its educational value. Thirdly, the limited time for interaction with each interlocutor may not allow you to work out the structure deeply enough. These difficulties can be solved by preliminary preparation of students: before the start of the "carousel" the teacher can conduct a mini-instruction, provide examples, and also include a self-check or reflection stage after completing the exercise. An effective addition to the "Carousel" is the "Snowball Method", which helps to deepen the study of the material. This approach promotes the active work of all students, excluding passive observation. Each student is involved in the process and has the opportunity to repeat the material several times in conversational practice, which makes the study of grammar more lively, interesting and productive.

The Snowball method is a game-based form of learning, where each subsequent participant must not only use a new grammatical construction, but also correctly repeat all the previous ones. In the context of grammar teaching, this method allows you to consolidate and learn the rules through repetition and gradual addition of new elements. It effectively develops both memory and the skills of practical application of grammatical structures. The goal of the game is not only to teach how to correctly formulate sentences in various constructions, but also to develop

memory, attention and reaction speed. Gradually, students accumulate a grammatical "snowball", where each new element of grammar is integrated into the information already learned. It is important that each subsequent element is syntactically and logically connected with the previous ones, which contributes to the systemic perception of the language. For example, students are given the task of composing a logically coherent text using the passive voice in English, while the teacher himself sets the initial sentence, for example, *The book has been written by Mary*. Each student should repeat the previous sentence and add their own, for example, *Then it has been brought to bookshop by John*. The student who breaks the chain of sentences is eliminated from the game, the next student is given a new sentence, and a new text begins. The main thing is that during the game, students not only repeat grammatical constructions, but also actively use them, which contributes to better memorization. In addition, this creates an element of competition: students want not only to use grammar correctly, but also not to forget all the previous sentences. This approach develops both motivation and concentration, since each new element requires attentiveness from the participants.

Despite the high efficiency of the Snowball method in developing memory and automating grammatical structures, it also has some disadvantages that can reduce the effectiveness of learning. Students with a low level of language proficiency or weak short-term memory may experience stress due to the need to memorize long chains of sentences, which distracts them from grammatical accuracy. Under limited time conditions, not all students have time to actively participate in the game, and waiting for their turn can turn into passive observation. In addition, the game format sometimes shifts the emphasis from meaningful analysis of grammatical structures to the desire to simply not make mistakes, which reduces the educational value of the exercise. These difficulties can be overcome by adjusting the complexity of the tasks and the number of repetitions taking into account the level of the group, as well as supplementing the game with elements of self-assessment and discussion, including analysis of typical errors and composing a written version of the story after completing the task. An alternative approach to teaching grammar aimed at developing meaningful use of language is the problem-based learning method. It is based on solving real or simulated situations in which students apply grammatical constructions in the context of analysis, discussion and search for solutions.

Problem-based learning (PBL) – This is an unconventional pedagogical technology in which students act as subjects of the educational process and solve the task set before them together. According to researchers, PBL entered foreign language education from the medical field in the 50-60s of the last century. This was caused by the lack of critical thinking skills in students and the need to move away from reproductive forms of education and move to search, research methods. [1] This approach is especially relevant in improving the grammatical competence of future English teachers, since with the help of problem-based learning, students have the opportunity not only to improve their grammar skills, but also to learn how to solve pedagogical problems, simulating a real situation. The teacher in this situation acts not as a teacher, but as an organizer of the educational process and an observer of the course of events. At the same time, students study language material through solving practical problems, and not by mechanically memorizing rules. In traditional teaching, grammar is often presented in isolation - through rules and exercises. In PBL, grammatical structures are learned in context: students are faced with a communicative task that requires mastery of a specific grammar. In our case, since the passive voice is used in formal, scientific and news speech, the use of the problem-based method in

studying this structure makes the learning process practical and motivating for students. Below are some of the advantages of the problem-based approach to teaching Passive Voice:

– *meaningfulness and contextuality*: the passive voice is not an isolated grammatical unit, but a tool that allows changing the focus of the statement. Problem-based learning creates conditions for understanding why and in what situations the passive is used.

– *development of critical thinking*: problem-solving tasks encourage students to analyze the context, choose between active and passive constructions, and explain language choices.

– *motivation and engagement*: students do not receive rules "from above", but formulate them themselves, which arouses interest, increases motivation and a sense of satisfaction from discovery.

– *communicative orientation*: problematic situations most often model real communication tasks - description of incidents, reports, news - where the passive voice is appropriate and necessary.

Examples of the implementation of the problematic approach:

1. *Headline Analysis*: students are given news headlines with passive constructions ("A new law was passed", "Two people were injured"). The questions are discussed: who committed the action? why is he not named? is it possible to reformulate the sentence in the active form?

2. *Language investigation*: students are offered several sentences, including both active and passive ones. The task is to determine why this particular voice was chosen in each case and formulate a rule.

3. *Role game*: a staging of an incident (for example, a robbery), where some students are witnesses, others are journalists, and others are police officers. When describing the events, they must use passive constructions: "The window was broken", "The money was taken".

4. *Project work*: creating a wall newspaper or electronic magazine with school or city news, in which it is necessary to use at least 10 passive constructions.

Thus, the use of problem-based learning in studying the passive voice allows us to move from the formal acquisition of grammatical structures to meaningful and functional use of language. This approach helps develop students' linguistic intuition, increases interest in the subject, and activates their thinking. The passive voice is no longer perceived as an abstract rule, but becomes a working tool in real speech practice. Problem-based learning is justified both in terms of pedagogical effectiveness and in terms of developing universal learning skills. However, due to the high degree of independence, students may experience difficulties in setting goals and formulating hypotheses, especially with an insufficient level of language training. It is also possible that the content of the task will be overemphasized at the expense of grammatical accuracy: carried away by the search for a solution, students do not always control the correctness of grammatical forms. In addition, the process of organizing PBL itself requires significant time and effort from the teacher, especially when preparing high-quality tasks and supporting group work. These difficulties can be mitigated by preliminary briefings, well-chosen templates, and step-by-step support during the task, including language cues and intermediate control.

REFERENCES

1. Normala, Othman & Ahamad Shah, Mohamed. (2013). Problem-Based Learning in the English Language Classroom. *English Language Teaching*. 6. 125-134. 10.5539/elt.v6n3p125.

2. Остапова Л.Е. К проблеме развития грамматических навыков и умений в процессе обучения иностранному языку. *Форум молодых ученых*. № 1 (5), 2017. С. 429-432

3. Сакаева Л.Р., Баранова А.Р. Методика обучения иностранным языкам (учебное пособие для студентов Института математики и механики им. Н.И. Лобачевского по направлению «педагогическое образование (с двумя профилями подготовки)»). – Казань, КФУ, 2016. С. 66-68